

Short Communication

Facile Preparation of Gadolinium Conversion Coating for Dental Application

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The usage of biodegradable screws and plates for bone healing prevents revision surgery. Magnesium and its alloys are one of the widely researched bio-resorbable materials for the possible usage as implant material due to their mechanical properties and non-toxicity. In the present study, conversion coating with gadolinium was done. The formation of nanoplatelets covered with spindle-shaped structures was seen. The formation of gadolinium oxide was confirmed with Attenuated total reflectance-infrared spectroscopy (ATR-IR). The real-time corrosion monitoring was performed using hydrogen evolution studies.

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Introduction

The restoration of damaged bone in the maxillofacial region with the degradable implant material is one of the upcoming fields in dentistry [1]. The usage of biodegradable screws and plates for bone healing prevents revision surgery [2]. Magnesium and its alloys are one of the widely researched bioresorbable materials for possible usage as implant material due to their mechanical properties and non-toxicity [3]. Mg is one among the most abundant micronutrient in the body and is directly related to various biological reactions [4]. Despite the panoply properties of Mg and its alloys, its corrosion rate is uncontrollable leading to the hyper-generation of hydrogen and local hiking of pH [5].

In the search for reducing the corrosion rate of Mg alloy, the formation of conversion coating is an efficient process. In the present study, we have conversion coating with gadolinium on AZ31 Mg alloy. The rare-earth element gadolinium can decline the rate of corrosion in Mg due to its scavenging effect on the impurities [6]. Also, gadolinium ions support the osseointegration in the bone and can be removed from the body through urine [7].

Materials and Methods

AZ31 Mg alloy sheet (prepared and gifted by Seoul National University) was cut into rectangular shapes with the dimensions of 25 mm × 15 mm × 10 mm. The rectangular shaped AZ31 Mg alloy was polished mechanically using the silicon carbide sheet up to 1000. The grease present on the sample was removed by acetone and then using double distilled water and dried. The prepared Mg samples were immersed in 0.5 % Gadolinium nitrate for 20 min at room temperature.

The surface morphology of the sample was analysed with TESCO-VEGA3 Scanning electron microscope (SEM) and the elemental composition using an energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX). The surface functional group of the sample from 4000 to 500 cm⁻¹ using Attenuated Total Reflectance-Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-IR) Perkin Elmer Spectrum two, USA.

The bare and the coated sample were immersed in simulated body fluid (SBF) and the evolved hydrogen was collected in a burette placed above a funnel. The composition of SBF was provided in the previous literature [8]. The corrosion rate of the samples was evaluated from the hydrogen evolution studies [9].

Results and Discussion

Figure 1 shows the conversion coating formulated using gadolinium at various magnifications. The formed coating displayed the nanoplate-like morphology covered with spindle-

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Figure 1: SEM image of conversion coating and the corresponding EDX profile

shaped structures on the surface, which is seen clearly in the magnified image Fig 1 b. The nano-morphological structure provides the necessary physical cues to support cell adhesion [10]. The presence of magnesium, gadolinium and oxygen is observed in the EDX profile.

ATR-IR spectra of bare and conversion coating are displayed in Figure 2. In the bare, the broad peak at 700-400 cm^{-1} corresponds to the interaction of Mg and O on the implant surface. In conversion

coating, the broadband at 3750-3000 cm^{-1} is attributed to stretching vibration of -OH [9]. The Gd-O-Gd and Gd=O interaction is ascertained by the peak at 1365 and 1405 cm^{-1} [11]. The peak at 525 cm^{-1} depicted the interaction of metal and oxygen in Mg-O and Gd_2O_3 [7]. From the ATR-IR studies, it is confirmed that the gadolinium oxide coating formation on AZ31 Magnesium alloy.

The hydrogen evolution from the bare and conversion coating was analysed by immersing in the SBF solution. In bare, initial hydrogen evolution was drastic and then attained stability after 5 days. The large quantity of hydrogen evolved from the bare is due to the unstable oxide formation on the surface at pH 7.4. After which, the difference in hydrogen evolution was minimum due to the rise in the pH of the solution [12]. From the conversion coating, the evolution of hydrogen was very minimal. The cumulative release of hydrogen was around 0.14 mL after seven days of immersion in SBF.

From the obtained hydrogen evolution, the rate of corrosion was calculated. In bare, the corrosion rate was fluctuating (i.e) increasing and decreasing. The corrosion rate was minimal throughout the duration indicating the stability of the coating.

Conclusion

The conversion coating with gadolinium was fabricated on AZ31 Mg alloy. The coating showed the morphology of nanoplatelets with spindle-like structures on them. The ATR-IR studies confirmed the presence of gadolinium oxide on AZ31 Mg alloy. The real-time corrosion rate of the conversion coating monitored from the hydrogen evolution studies was minimal.

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Figure 2: ATR-IR spectra of bare and conversion coating

Figure 3: Hydrogen evolution and the calculated corrosion rate of bare and conversion coating

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